

Multifunctional Composites with Easy-Repairing and Integrated Damage Sensing Capabilities

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The Thermoset Composite Lifecycle

Manufacture

Service Life

End of Life

The Thermoset Composite Lifecycle

Manufacture

**Increased
Service Life**

End of Life

Easy Repairing

Patch it up!

Bonded/Bolted Patch

Replace it!

Scarf/Stepped Lap

Scarf

Stepped Lap

Patch it up!

Bonded/Bolted Patch

Replace it!

Scarf/Stepped Lap

*What if the structure
isn't easy to move?*

Thermoplastic blending
(*repair with heat*)

Pioneering science, but what
are the engineering
challenges?

Thermoplastic blending

Pioneering science, but what are the engineering challenges?

Thermal Properties

Environmental Barrier

High Viscosity Processing

Thermoplastic Phenoxy

- High T_g (90°C)
- A known toughening agent

Interleaving

- Scalable
- Localized
- Liquid Resin Compatible

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Initial Fracture Toughness

430% ↑ Toughness

(0.34 kJ/m² → 1.81 kJ/m²)

110% ↑ Maximum Load

(34.7 N → 72.9 N)

After 1st Repair

Repaired but with
Reduced Toughness

No Change to Maximum
Load

Outperforming Reference

After 2nd Repair

Stabilised Toughness

Slight Loss of Peak Load

3rd & 4th Repairing...

Small Declines in
Toughness

Steady Decline in P_{\max}

After 1st Fracture

After 5th Fracture

Pristine Laminate

After Fracture / Before Repair

After Repair

When to Repair?

Measure through-thickness Resistance during Fracture

Carbon/Epoxy

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Carbon/Epoxy

Measure through-thickness Resistance during Fracture

Phenoxy Interleaved
1st fracture

Measure through-thickness Resistance during Fracture

Phenoxy Interleaved
2nd fracture

Measure through-thickness Resistance during Fracture

Phenoxy Interleaved
3rd fracture

Measure through-thickness Resistance during Fracture

Phenoxy Interleaved
4th fracture

Measure through-thickness Resistance during Fracture

Phenoxy Interleaved
5th fracture

Measure through-thickness Resistance during Fracture

Phenoxy Interleaved
5th fracture

- Repeatably repairable composite demonstrated

Structural Health Monitoring

- Potential to detect damage after repairing

- Optimizing service life in toughened components

Read our open access paper: "Smart and repeatable easy-repairing and self-sensing composites with enhanced mechanical performance for extended components life"

Composites Part A

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